

Physics-Informed Transfer Functions for Accelerated Coupled Monte Carlo Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Coupled Monte Carlo (MC)–thermal-hydraulic simulations are becoming increasingly feasible as computational resources improve, yet their widespread use still requires effective acceleration strategies. This work introduces a physics-informed transfer function (PTF) method designed to predict multigroup macroscopic cross sections with minimal user input while preserving the accuracy of expanded transfer function (ETF) approaches. The PTF method incorporates physically meaningful features by estimating the contributions of neutrons born in each material region and tracking how they distribute their collisions throughout the core using fixed-source Coarse mesh finite difference (CMFD) calculations. These source-contribution fractions and optical system parameters replace the extensive geometry-based indicators required by ETF methods. Additionally, a volume-based trivial equivalence theory (TET) is implemented to ensure CMFD solutions remain equivalent to the reference MC solutions without relying on high-uncertainty surface-current tallies. The method is demonstrated on a NERVA-type nuclear thermal propulsion reactor model using multiple core snapshots with varying control drum positions and thermal-hydraulic conditions. Results show that the PTF model reproduces the fission production cross section behavior with accuracy comparable to ETF predictions while significantly reducing the required setup effort. The PTF approach therefore provides a practical and user-friendly path toward accelerating fully coupled Monte Carlo analyses.

Keywords: Multiphysics, Monte Carlo, Transfer Functions, CMFD

1. INTRODUCTION

Recent advancements in computational architecture have enabled the use of Monte Carlo for full core analyses of nuclear reactors. These analyses have increasingly involved coupled Monte Carlo calculations, including coupled thermal hydraulic analysis [1, 2, 3, 4] and even transient simulations. These coupled applications become significantly more feasible with reliable acceleration methods. Such methods are especially suitable when they (1) do not require a pre-generation stage, (2) impose minimal additional overhead on the Monte Carlo simulation, and (3) operate reliably with minimal user input. Of interest to this work is an acceleration approach that works in two stages. In the first stage, group constants are predicted using a linear model [5, 6]. In the second stage, the group constants are fed to a CMFD solver to produce an updated spatial flux distribution [7].

The most recent approach to cross section prediction—expanded transfer functions (ETFs)—is generally very accurate. However, ETFs require significant set up from a user standpoint. Users must provide an explicit representation of the geometry, pick a suitable uniform grid of points for convolutions, and identify the most important feedback parameters. Often, trial and error is needed to achieve reliably accurate results with ETFs [6].

CMFD solvers often introduce significant overhead in Monte Carlo simulations. This is because the standard CMFD equivalence approach requires surface current tallies [7]. These surface tallies often require more statistics to achieve acceptable uncertainty [8].

This work introduces two novelties to the proposed acceleration technique. The first is a more physically rigorous definition of the transfer function technique that requires significantly less user input. In the new technique, distance and direction-based treatment of thermal-hydraulic variables are approximated using an equivalent CMFD model. The second novelty is a simple volume-based

equivalence approach. The latter approach requires no iteration to obtain equivalence factors unlike superhomogenization factors or JFNK-UDFs.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the codes and methods used in this work. Section 3 describes the reactor problem explored in this work. Section 4 presents results and Section 5 concludes the paper.

2. METHODOLOGY

Section 2.1 briefly describes the codes and software used in this work. Section 2.2 through section **Error! Reference source not found.** the basic methodology of the CMFD solver in pyCMFD. Section 2.4 describes the novel physics-informed transfer function method.

2.1. Codes

All CMFD calculations are carried out using the open-source, python-based package pyCMFD. Linear modeling of cross section is carried out using a coupled calculation between pyCMFD and the open-source python package xsfit [6]. Thermal hydraulic variables are calculated through the sub-channel code Core-ThM [9, 10]. Finally, all Monte Carlo calculations are carried out through Serpent [11].

2.2. CMFD Summary

This sub section describes the interface leakage relations used in pyCMFD. For convenience, an equivalent resistance is defined as,

$$R_u^i = \frac{|\Delta_u^i|}{D_{g,u}}, \quad (1)$$

where $|\Delta_u^i|$ represents the distance between the centroid of volume u and the centroid of the interface i on volume u . $D_{g,u}$ represents the diffusion coefficient in region u and group g . The CMFD surface-integrated leakage [12] from region u to region u' satisfies the relationship below,

$$L_{g,u \rightarrow u'}^i = -\frac{\phi_{g,u'} - \phi_{g,u}}{R_{g,u'}^i + R_{g,u}^i} A^i, \quad (2)$$

where A^i is the surface area of interface i between region u and region u' . $f_{g,u}^i$ is the discontinuity factor on interface i in group g on the side of region u . The CMFD leakage from region u into an albedo boundary is [12, 13],

$$L_{g,u \rightarrow \Gamma}^i = \frac{\phi_{g,u}}{R_{g,\Gamma}^i + R_{g,u}^i} A^i, \quad (3)$$

where the equivalent resistance of the albedo region at interface i and in group g ($R_{g,\Gamma}^i$) is defined as,

$$R_{g,\Gamma}^i = 2 \frac{1 + \alpha_g^i}{1 - \alpha_g^i}, \quad (4)$$

where α_g^i is the albedo coefficient on interface i and in group g .

pyCMFD solves eigenvalue problems using a standard inner/outer iteration approach [15]. On outer iterations, the source due to fissions is held constant such that

$$s_{g,u}^{(j+1)} = \frac{1}{k^{(j)}} \frac{1}{\zeta_k} \chi_{g,u} \sum_{g'=1}^G \nu \Sigma_{f,g',u} \zeta_{g',u} \phi_{g',u}^{(j)} V_u \quad (5)$$

Where $k^{(j)}$ is the eigenvalue and $\phi_{g',u}^{(j)}$ is the flux in group g' and in region u in the j^{th} outer iteration. $s_{g,u}^{(j+1)}$ is therefore the fixed source in the $(j+1)^{th}$ outer iteration that represents the contributions due to fissions.

On inner iterations (denoted by k), the source due to in-scattering and fissions is held constant such that,

$$q_{g,u}^{(j+1),(k+1)} = \sum_{g'=1}^G \Sigma_{sp,g' \rightarrow g,u} \zeta_{g',u} \phi_{g',u}^{(j+1),(k)} V_u + s_{g,u}^{(j+1)}, \quad (6)$$

Where $\phi_{g',u}^{(j+1),(k)}$ is the flux in group g' and in region u for the $(j+1)^{th}$ outer iteration and k^{th} inner iteration. $q_{g,u}^{(j+1),(k+1)}$ is therefore the fixed source in the $(j+1)^{th}$ outer iteration and $(k+1)^{th}$ inner iteration that represents the contributions due to fissions and in-scatterings.

2.3. Trivial Equivalence Theory

The standard approach to ensuring CMFD equivalence is to establish a set of “closure” relations at each interface and on each albedo boundary of the CMFD solution. These closures ensure the CMFD solution produces the same net surface currents as a reference heterogenous solution. However, this approach is difficult to implement when generating data from a full core Monte Carlo solution. This is because surface tallies have a much higher uncertainty than volume-based tallies. These tallies are also highly dependent on the MC method (e.g., ray tracing or Delta tracking). Thus, this work will employ a simple volume-based correction approach. Beyond pin power reconstruction, the reactor physics community tends to avoid conserving equivalence through the following approach,

$$\tilde{\phi}_{g,u}^{hom} = \phi_{g,u}^{hom} \times \zeta_{g,u}, \quad (7)$$

$$\tilde{k}^{hom} = k^{hom} \times \zeta_k, \quad (8)$$

where ζ denotes a correction factor that directly conserves equivalence of the flux and eigenvalue. The authors thus refer to this technique as trivial equivalence theory (TET). The authors would like to note that the flux correction factors defined above have previously been investigated [14] for making a multigroup MC solution equivalent to a continuous energy MC solution. These were referred to as “form functions.” However, that work did not include an eigenvalue correction factor.

2.4. Physics-Informed Transfer Functions

The PTF methodology is only briefly introduced in this section. A more detailed explanation and derivation of the PTF method is saved for future work. Briefly, the PTF model uses a relies on a CMFD solution to estimate the response matrix for a given neutron transport problem. This response matrix is used to construct features that explicitly represent how much an input in a nonlocal region u' affects the macroscopic cross section in a local region u . The PTF model is given as follows,

$$\Sigma_{x,g,u} - \Sigma_{x,g,m}^* \approx \sum_{i \in u} \left(\frac{\partial \Sigma_{x,g,m}}{\partial N_{m,i,t}} \right) (N_{u,i,t} - N_{m,i,t}^*) + \sum_{m'} \left(\frac{\partial \Sigma_{x,g,m}}{\partial I_{g,u,i,t}^{m'}} \right) (I_{g,u,i,t}^{m'} - I_{g,u,i,t}^{m',*}). \quad (9)$$

Where $\Sigma_{x,g,u}$ is the value for a macroscopic cross section of reaction type x in group g and in region u . $\Sigma_{x,g,m}^*$ is a nominal or average value for $\Sigma_{x,g}$ in material region m . Region u belongs exclusively to material region m . $N_{u,i,t}$ is a relative number density for input i at state t in region u . All $N_{u,i,t}$ values represent the “local” effects of system parameters on the cross section in region u . $I_{g,u,i,t}^{m'}$ represents the “influence” of input i at state t in material m' on region u in group g . All $I_{g,u,i,t}^{m'}$ values represent nonlocal effects on the local macroscopic cross section. The exact definitions of $N_{u,i,t}$ and $I_{g,u,i,t}^{m'}$ are given in the following sections.

2.4.1. Local Parameters

Consider a case where the rotation of a control drum is to be modeled in the PTF. One could construct a feature that represents the continuous value of the control drum angle. The alternative approach, used here, is to represent any continuous value for the control drum angle as a linear combination of discrete control drum angles. Here, linear interpolation is specifically used. If the control drum angle in region u is 10° , then this rotation is represented as a 50/50 mixture of the control drum at 0° and at 20° as depicted in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Representation of control drum angles using linear combination of discrete values.

2.4.2. Nonlocal Parameters

Nonlocal influences are a combination of two factors. The first is the source contribution factor $F_{g,u}^{m'}$ which represents the fraction of neutrons that collide in region u and in group g that are born in material m' . The second factor is the “optical” number density $\bar{N}_{g,u,i,t}^{m'}$ of input i at state t in material m' as seen by region u in group g . The nonlocal influence $I_{g,u,i,t}^{m'}$ is thus given as,

$$I_{g,u,i,t}^{m'} = F_{g,u}^{m'} \times \bar{N}_{g,u,i,t}^{m'} \quad (10)$$

Thus, a nonlocal influence represents the average value of a nonlocal parameter as seen by region u scaled by the number of neutrons that stream into region u from a nonlocal material m' .

2.4.3. Calculation of Source Contribution Fractions

As mentioned above, the PTF requires the calculation of “source contribution fractions.” To calculate these factors, the following series of fixed source problems are solved for each material type m' ,

$$\underline{H}_g \underline{\phi}_g^{m'} = \underline{q}_g \circ \underline{\delta}^{m'}, \quad (11)$$

where $\underline{\delta}^{m'}$ is a delta function that is equal to one for all regions associated with material type m' and is zero otherwise. \circ denotes the element-wise Hadamard product between two vectors. $\underline{\phi}_g^{m'}$ is therefore the neutron population in group g as a response to the total source in all regions associated with material type m' . The fractional contribution of the sources in material type m' and in group g is then calculated using,

$$F_{g,u}^{m'} = \frac{\phi_{g,u}^{m'}}{\phi_{g,u}} \quad (12)$$

2.4.4. Calculation of “Optical” System Parameters

The PTF also requires the calculation of “optical” values for system parameters as seen by region u . To calculate this “optical” property, the following weighted fixed source problem is solved,

$$\underline{H}_g \eta_{g,u,i,t}^{m'} = \underline{S}_g \circ \underline{N}_{i,t} \circ \underline{\delta}^{m'} \quad (13)$$

Then, optical system parameters are extracted using,

$$\bar{N}_{g,u,i,t}^{m'} = \frac{\eta_{g,u,i,t}^{m'}}{\phi_{g,u}^{m'}} \quad (14)$$

2.4.5. Linear Regression

Once all relevant features have been calculated, the following linear regression for a single core state is established and then solved,

$$\underline{X}_g^{(n)} \underline{w}_{x,g} = \underline{\Sigma}_{x,g}^{(n)} \quad (15)$$

Where the columns of $\underline{X}_g^{(n)}$ contain all relevant features for state n and in group g . Here “features” refers to region-wise values of $I_{g,u}^{m',i',t}$ and $N_{u,i,t}$ variables as shown in equation (9). Each element of $w_{y,g}$ describes a different weight in equation (9). Multiple states can be used to inform the regression by vertically stacking $\underline{X}_g^{(n)}$ and $\underline{\Sigma}_{x,g}^{(n)}$.

The goal is now to calculate a set of weights $w_{x,g}$ that minimizes the error between the Serpent-generated cross sections and the cross sections predicted by the linear model. *xsfit* uses the RidgeCV object from scikit-learn to first perform cross validation on a ridge regression [17]. *xsfit* also uses sklearn’s StandardScaler object to normalize \underline{X}_g before regression so that the magnitude of each weight is penalized equally in the ridge regression [17].

3. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

The model explored in this work is based off a NERVA-type NTP rocket core. The complete description of the model, including the optimization of the fuel loading pattern, can be found in Ref. [18]. In this work, thermal hydraulic conditions are assigned to the six different “sectors” in the core. Material temperatures in each sector are visualized in Figure 2a below and the axial distribution of material temperatures are visualized in Figure 2b below. Starting with the top right sector and moving clockwise, the TH conditions in each sector correspond to 0%, 36%, 4%, 64%, 16%, and 100% nominal core power (about 300 MW). In each of the 10 snapshots of the core, half the drums are rotated to one angle, and the other half are rotated to a completely different angle. The drum angle in degrees for each snapshot are reported in Table I. A zero (0) degree drum rotation corresponds to the B_4C absorber shim being rotated completely outward. Each core snapshot is not a realistic representation of a core state. Rather, they are useful for stress testing the PTF method and are a convenient choice for generating a database for fitting the PTF model with relatively few MC executions.

Table I. Control drum angles for each core snapshot.

Snapshot ID	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	B1	B2	B3	B4	B5
Right side angle (degrees)	0	20	40	60	80	100	120	140	160	180
Left side angle (degrees)	100	120	140	160	180	0	20	40	60	80

Homogenized group constants are generated using the overlaid hexagonal mesh depicted in Figure 3 below. Homogenization zones are a series of concentric “rings.” This choice ensures that

homogenization regions on the periphery of the core attain reasonable statistics. Figure 2b shows the seventeen axial homogenization regions in the core. In total there are 1139 unique homogenization zones in the core.

Figure 2. Radial (a) and axial (b) view of core snapshot A1.

Figure 3. Visualization of the concentric ring homogenization scheme in the top right sector.

Each core snapshot was performed in Serpent on 24 threads of an Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6226 CPU (2.70 GHz) node. There were 380 active cycles and 80 inactive cycles simulated, each with 700,000 particles. In total each MC execution took 45 hours.

4. RESULTS

As a basic demonstration of the PTF method, core snapshots A1, A2, A3, A4, and A5 are used to calculate weights for the PTF model. Then, cross sections in core snapshot B1 are predicted. For conciseness, only the results for the fission-production cross section and flux correction factors in the 0% (sector a) and 64% (sector d) power sectors are plotted. Figure 4a and Figure 5a compare the serpent and PTF results for the fission-production cross section. Figure 4b and Figure 5b compare the serpent and PTF results for the flux correction factors. These results indicate that the PTF model performs well at fitting to and predicting cross section data correction factors, even for large drum rotations.

— * State a1 (Serpent/PTF)
— * State b1 (Serpent/PTF)

— * State a1 (Serpent/PTF)
— * State b1 (Serpent/PTF)

Figure 4. Reference and predicted corrected fission production values in ring 7 and (a) sector d and (b) sector (a) of the core.

Figure 5. Reference and predicted flux correction factor values in ring 7 and (a) sector d and (b) sector (a) of the core.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The application of Monte Carlo (MC) codes to coupled analyses is becoming increasingly feasible as modern computational architecture improves. Still, some form of acceleration via reduced-order prediction is crucial to making coupled MC analysis feasible. This work builds on a previously established approach to acceleration which involves a linear model to predict cross sections and a CMFD solver to predict fluxes. Specifically, the CMFD model has been adapted to simplify and improve the linear macroscopic cross section model. Previously, distance and direction-based effects were captured only through linear regression. In this novel physics-informed transfer function (PTF) method, the CMFD estimates distance-based effects by tracking how source neutrons propagate in a problem.

The PTF method has been shown to produce accurate predictions of the cross sections of the fission production. Additionally, the PTF model is significantly more user-friendly than the former expanded transfer function (ETF) method. The PTF method thus appears to be a more practical path forward for accelerating coupled Monte Carlo analyses.

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